

An aerial photograph of a rocky coastline. The rocks are covered in vibrant, multi-colored algae in shades of purple, blue, and red. Pools of clear blue water are scattered among the rocks. In the foreground, a sandy beach meets the ocean. A person wearing a red wetsuit is walking on the beach, carrying a white surfboard under their arm.

Final exploitation workshop - Milestone 11

ICONS – Chiara Bartolacci, Giovanni Amigoni

WP5 – Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation

T5.6 - Sustainability of results and consolidation of post-project exploitation

16/01/2025 - Mafra

Objectives

1. Update the list of results to be achieved by the end of the project and focus on the post-project phase (exploitation and project legacy)
2. Take stock of progress made for programming and prioritising project activities during the final six months.
3. Operationalise the work conducted so far, aligning with reviewers' recommendations.
4. Summarise the work done on the arenas to date, developing a strategic tool to support stakeholders' engagement.

Materials

- Material considered:
 - The list of Key Exploitable Results (KERs) identified in D5.1 (M6).
 - The list of outcomes identified by WP1, WP2 and WP3 for dissemination purposes.
 - The stakeholder analysis in D5.4 (M14).
 - Reports from the three TAWs.
- Templates developed:
 1. Consolidation and update of the project result list.
 2. Exploitation canvas for each arena.

1st session - Consolidation and update of project result lists

Timing: 45 min

Organisation: 3 groups based on WPs

Activities:

- Review the results (3 KERs and sub-KERs, including clusterisation if needed) based on the project's expected outcomes.
- Cross-check the outcomes list to ensure all are mapped and addressed (note: outcomes highlighted in fuchsia are currently missing from the results list).

Open questions to address

- Refine and prioritize the description of results, also considering the questions to be submitted to the EKLIPSE process.
- Update KER1 description in light of framework progress from yesterday
- Update KER2 description with new information related to the OPPLA platform
- Since WP₄ has no defined outcomes, we could use this opportunity to finalise WP₄ outcomes and integrate Arenas' results (e.g., Trento Arena Manifesto, Capacity Gaps for Implementation).
- Describe and add the Card game to the result list.

→ **About this template**

The template presents two tables:
 1) BioValue results that were mapped and clustered through the exploitation questionnaires and included in DS.1
 2) BioValue outcomes that were defined for dissemination purposes.

Please:
 1- Outline the correspondence among outcomes and results
 2- If necessary, update, revise, move the project results in the list or add new ones, in light of the outcomes

Grab a sticky and position it on the KERs table!

OUTCOMES		
WP1	OUTCOME NUMBER	TITLE
1	1	Current challenges and barriers to biodiversity inclusion in spatial planning and management instruments
1	3	Framework for integration of Ecosystem Service mapping and assessment in Spatial Planning
1	4	Spatial planning instruments with potential to protect, restore or enhance biodiversity, and implementation best practices
1	5	Urban ecosystem mapping and condition assessment to support planning for biodiversity
1	1	Benchmarking biodiversity: How well are we integrating biodiversity in environmental assessment
2	2	Enhancing biodiversity in spatial planning: A systems thinking approach to environmental assessment with causal loop diagrams
2	3	Mitigation and enhancement (no title yet)
2	4	Integration of Environmental Assessment and causal loop tool in the spatial planning process (title to be found)
2	5	Tiering (title to be found)
3	1	Economic and Financial Instruments to Enhance Biodiversity Outcomes
3	2	Impacts of Economic and Financial Instruments on Biodiversity in Spatial Planning
3	3	(working title) Implications from the EU renewed Sustainable Finance Strategy for Spatial Planning
3	4	(working title) Exploring Ecosystem Service Opportunities in Spatial Planning

BioValue planning game - Set of cards representing the mapped instruments to be used in spatial planning decision-making process - UniTrento, IST-ID, AAU, UFZ

1st session - Consolidation and update of project result lists

Template

RESULTS (KERs)

KER1. Analytical framework for biodiversity transformative change in spatial policy and planning	IST-ID, AAU, UFZ, UniTrento
1A - Adaptation and upscaling of existing conceptual and analytical framework for spatial planning, to explore the transformative potential of the three instrumental perspectives.	
1B - Multi-level governance transformative proposals promoting policy mixes to be replicated across EU Member States.	

KER2. A set of tools for spatial planning transformations	IST-ID, AAU, UFZ, UniTrento
2A - BioValue interactive platform, a tool for sharing data, information and knowledge as well as co-producing new knowledge on spatial planning.	
2B - Collection and selection of innovative tools, methods, methodologies for innovative policy and planning development, including:	
<i>Spatial Planning and Management Instruments (SP&MI)</i>	
Spatial Planning instruments that proved to be the most relevant for transformational change on biodiversity, selected from existing platforms and information sharing mechanisms.	UniTrento, IST-ID, AAU, UFZ
Framework for the integration of Ecosystem Services (ES) and urban ecosystem mapping and assessment in spatial planning decisions to mainstream biodiversity value and to be applied as empirical and operative analysis in the case studies.	UniTrento, IST-ID, AAU, UFZ
<i>Environmental Assessment Instruments (EAI)</i>	
Environmental Assessment Instruments that proved to be the most effective in including and valuing biodiversity.	AAU, IST-ID, UFZ, UniTrento
Causal loop tool to improve the identification of causal connections in environmental assessment, promoting a system thinking approach.	AAU, IST-ID, UFZ, UniTrento
<i>Economic and financing economic and financial instruments (E&FIs)</i>	
Economic and Financial Instruments selected to promote biodiversity conservation and enhance ecosystem value during spatial-planning process.	UFZ, IST-ID, AAU, UniTrento
Proposal for improving the most promising Economic and Financial Instruments to enhance transformative change for biodiversity in spatial planning	UFZ, IST-ID, AAU, UniTrento

KER3. Guidelines on the pathways to include these tools in spatial planning	UniTrento, IST-ID, AAU, UFZ, CM Mafra, COMUNE TRENTO, CoKnow
Working methodologies and projects from the arenas for transformation as guidelines for integrating biodiversity into spatial planning local practices that enable the regeneration of biodiversity:	
Pathways to improving EAI transformative potential based on case study evidence and research activities.	AAU
Organic summary of recommendations for policymakers related to the implications of the EU Sustainable Finance Strategy for spatial planning.	UFZ
Provision of economic, social, and environmental data to provide evidence of biophysical, economic, and socio-cultural impacts of ES, and explore opportunities in spatial planning.	UniTrento

1st session - Consolidation and update of project result lists

Next steps

- Finalize and consolidate the list and description of results.
- Assess the exploitation potential of each result and detail partners' intentions through one-on-one calls or questionnaires.
- Update the exploitation strategy based on developments in the EKLIPSE process.
- Update the strategy considering updates on the OPPLA platform.
- Update the strategy to include outcomes from the final joint event (e.g., policy advocacy, white paper, collaborations with other cluster projects).

Key Exploitable Results (KERs)

BioValue's KERs follow, as last updated after Ericeira's GA, integrating the contributions received after the related request for inputs.

KER1. Analytical framework for biodiversity transformative change in spatial policy and planning.	IST-ID, AAU, UFZ, UniTrento
1A - Adaptation of existing conceptual and analytical framework for spatial planning, to explore the transformative potential of the three instrumental perspectives.	
1B - Guidance document on assessing the transformative potential of instruments, both individually and in combination.	

KER2. A set of tools for spatial planning transformations.	IST-ID, AAU, UFZ, UniTrento
2A - Integration of BioValue's outputs on Oppla's interactive platform to share data, information and knowledge and to co-produce new knowledge on spatial planning.	
2B - Analysis and selection of innovative tools, measures and actions for innovative policy and planning development, including:	
Spatial Planning and Management Instruments (SP&MIs)	
Assessment of the current capacity gap for implementing a transformative planning practice for biodiversity.	
SP&MIs with the most potential for transformational change for biodiversity, selected from actual planning documents, existing platforms and initiatives.	
Framework for the integration of Ecosystem Services (ES), ecosystem mapping and assessment in spatial planning decisions.	
Environmental Assessment Instruments (EAI)s	
Environmental Assessment Instruments that proved to be the most effective in including and valuing biodiversity.	
Causal loop tool to improve the identification of causal connections in environmental assessment, promoting a system thinking approach.	
Economic and Financial Instruments (E&FIs)	
Economic and Financial Instruments selected to promote biodiversity conservation and enhance ecosystem value during spatial planning process.	
Summary of potentials for spatial planning related to the EU renewed Sustainable Finance Strategy.	
2C - Catalogue/taxonomy of tools, providing a mapping by type and function.	

KER3. Recommendations on the pathways to include these tools in spatial planning.	UniTrento, IST-ID, AAU, UFZ, Mafra, Trento, CoKnow
3A - Working methodologies and projects from the arenas for transformation, to be employed as guidelines for integrating biodiversity into spatial planning local practices that enable the regeneration of biodiversity:	
Pathways to improve EIAs' transformative potential based on case study evidence and research activities.	AAU
Provision of economic, social, and environmental data to provide evidence of biophysical, economic, and socio-cultural impacts of ES, and explore opportunities in spatial planning.	
Proposal/recommendations for improving the transformative potential of Economic and Financial Instruments to enhance biodiversity in spatial planning.	UFZ
Guidance on selecting, designing, and implementing Economic and Financial Instruments within spatial planning processes	UFZ
Catalogue of enhancement and mitigation measures for biodiversity.	ALL
Significance of biological principles for spatial planning and environmental assessment.	
3B - Decision tree for guiding the selection of tools based on context-specific characteristics.	
3C - Pilot version of a collaborative game (a deck of cards based on the catalogue of tools) to facilitate/educate planning teams in the use/implementation/selection of BioValue's tools for enhancing biodiversity in spatial planning.	
3D - Replication/transferability insights for the BioValue framework and tools in other EU countries/contexts, from the Eklipse platform.	

2nd session - Exploitation canvas for each Arena

Timing: 60 min

Organisation: 3 groups based on the Arenas, with representative from each WPs (if possible)

Activities:

Build on the outcomes of WP₄ and WP₅ activities to populate the canvas boxes and create a comprehensive overview of each Arena

Main points to prioritise

- Update the Arenas' ambitions for the post-project phase.
- Based on the interventions identified during the three TAWs (and the analysis of capacity gaps for implementation), define a list of highly targeted actions to be implemented from the end of the project up to four years later (e.g., if capacity gaps reveal a lack of funding, a possible action could be mapping funding sources).
- Link the identified actions to project results or potential future advancements that could support their achievement (in collaboration with WP partners).

2nd session - Exploitation canvas for each Arena

Template

2nd session - Exploitation canvas for each Arenas

Next steps

- The Miro boards will be digitised, and links will be shared to complete the template.
- Once the template is completed, it will be uploaded as an outcome of the workshop, meeting the milestone 11, set for M34.
- Following the finalization of the canvas, specific points will be further explored through one-on-one interviews with the Arenas, aimed at preparing the final exploitation plan.

BioValue's Ambitions:

Ambition 1: spatial planning safeguards, restores, allows recovery and enhances biodiversity.

Ambition 2: spatial planning significantly contributes to balanced and responsible consumption and production (avoiding external social and environmental costs).

Ambition 3: spatial planning significantly contributes to reducing socioeconomic inequalities.

About this template

The Business Model Canvas **maps** out key actors, activities and resources, the value proposition and more. Here, it has been revised to **strategise** and inform the experimentation of BioValue's research framework.

The focus is on the **post-project exploitation**, providing a template for developing a short-run (4-year) action plan and presenting it to the outside.

ARENA AMBITION

Contextualisation:

Facilitate large scale rewetting for the main purpose of climate protection, entailing both ecological restoration and the emergence of a new form of regional identity grounded in sustainability. Consider the multi-level aspects of planning while bringing together actors from different sectors of society in the co-creation of the desirable future of the peatlands. Stakeholders envision a landscape that "gives back" in multiple ways: climate change mitigation, groundwater protection, energy and material production, heritage and identity, and a new form of pride.

What is the intended post-project ambition?

The Arena aims to stand as a demonstrator of how rural areas can innovate facing new challenges. Central to this vision is a shift in values, where "success" is no longer defined solely by economic productivity but by resilience, coexistence, and sense of place.

KEY STAKEHOLDERS AND MAIN ACTORS

Which stakeholders do you expect to be most relevant for the post-project exploitation?

- Nature Park Directorate (conservation, education, tourism)
- Municipality of Malchin (peatland manager, spatial planning)
- Local farmers and landowners (land use, biomass production, nature conservation)
- Civil society (schools, NGOs, restaurant operators)
- Regional, federal state and EU-level policymakers (lawmakers, funders)
- Universities and research institutions (pilot projects, land use innovation).

POLICY AND SPATIAL PLANNING FRAMEWORK

Which spatial planning law and regulations impact your Arena?

How is the regulatory environment expected to affect the post-project exploitation?

The arena is embedded in a multi-level governance context, where a state-level Climate Protection Law currently aims for carbon neutrality by 2040. SEA and EIA are operational, though not yet fully aligned with proactive biodiversity enhancement. Spatial planning instruments such as land-use zoning, conservation areas, and ecosystem service mapping are in use, but require resources and integration of enhancement mandates. The Nature Park serves as a key institutional anchor, despite lacking regulatory authority. Climate protection is not yet implemented fully in spatial policies and other instruments like carbon certificates remain at a small-scale. Long-term land use transitions have been influenced by legacy drainage systems and shifting subsidy regimes. Economic incentives for rewetted soils are still not capable of pushing towards large-scale land-use change, and a value-chain for produce from rewetted soils is to be developed.

IMPLEMENTATION ACTIVITIES AND ROADMAP

What activities will the Arena ambition and transformative change be achieved through?

- Small-scale rewetting and monitoring (led by Nature Park and pioneering landowners)
- Development of biodiversity-sensitive land-use planning
- Community excursions, storytelling, and arts-based education
- Biomass harvesting and decentralized heating infrastructure
- Partnership with university research on land conservation.

What exploitation roadmap is envisioned to reach the intended post-project ambition?

- Mainstream biodiversity in multi-level planning, integrating an innovative SEA approach into the Climate Protection Law's implementation
- Expand biomass energy networks using rewetted hay species, and support the development of sustainable value chains for rewetted peatland-produced biomass
- Boundary organisations to help coordinating and mediating between interests and actors
- Nature Park as a living lab, catalysing experiential social learning.

KEY INSTRUMENTS AND TOOLS

Which instruments do you expect to employ for the post-project exploitation?

- **SEA/EIA:** Land ownership adjustment, conservation zoning, compensation measures, qualitative ecological standards
- **EAs:** SEA/EIA with biodiversity enhancement
- **E&Fs:** Economic incentives for biomass production through agricultural subsidies (although few incentives to develop a biomass processing value chain exist), public-private project coalitions, agri-environmental climate-related subsidies for biomass and restoration, public knowledge exchange platforms, regional development programs.

KEY RESOURCES

Which resources are expected to be crucial for the post-project exploitation?

Which ones are not currently present and will have to be sourced or developed?

- **Human and social capital:** multi-disciplinary expertise in ecology, land use planning and hydrology, biomass production and use, trust networks being built among landowners, the park team, innovative actors and civil society members, community engagement and active involvement from civil society actors and NGOs
- **Financial and economic resources:** payments from the CAP, national climate and biodiversity programs, and federal state and local private investment in biomass infrastructure
- **Data and knowledge infrastructures:** spatial maps, monitoring tools, Oppla platform content.

CONTRIBUTION AND RESULTS FROM BIOVALUE

Detail the role of Key Exploitable Results in the Arena

- **ERR1:** The analytical framework has helped identify how existing planning processes fall short of delivering biodiversity gains and what are the limitations of SEA/EIA implementation
- **ERR2:** BioValue explored alternative instruments beyond traditional land-use zoning, focusing on biomass heating (E&Fs)
- **ERR3:** BioValue provided tools (e.g., card game) to support local training, stakeholder workshops, and educational formats.

In terms of contributions during the project, BioValue:

- Helped identify and classify challenges for large-scale rewetting and instruments suitable to the local context
- Provided a platform to create a shared vocabulary and structure for interdisciplinary collaboration
- Provided a SEA policy brief improving understanding of how an innovative SEA approach could help foster biodiversity mainstreaming in Climate Protection Law implementation
- Emphasised linking scientific evidence with participatory formats, which were successfully piloted.

In terms of post-project activities:

- The card game (KER3) is an adaptable tool for future stakeholder training and education
- The integration of the tools catalogue (KER2) into digital platforms supports continued access to instruments
- The arena can be a demonstration case within the EU policy dialogue.

VALUE PROPOSITION

What motivates the intervention in the specific Arena context? What transformations will be achieved in your Arena? How do these relate to and build towards the post-project ambition?

The Arena is centered on climate-smart, biodiversity-enhancing land stewardship. It offers a replicable model for rural sustainability that combines rewetting expertise, community engagement formats, and energy transition solutions. For funders, the Arena demonstrates high alignment with EU Green Deal goals, nature restoration targets, and climate neutrality commitments. For regional actors, it is a source of identity and socio-ecological cohesion.

The Arena's ability to mobilise local actors, blend traditional land knowledge with scientific expertise, and deliver visible environmental benefits makes it a valuable site for long-term investment and strategic partnerships.

BARRIERS AND CHALLENGES

Which are the main barriers and challenges foreseen for post-project exploitation?

- Lack of binding authority for the Nature Park
- Fragmented land ownership and governance (70+ individual agreements cited)
- Technical difficulty of operating in wet soils and loss of fertile topsoil
- Social conflicts over land use priorities (e.g., between conservation and meat production)
- Gaps in biomass value chain and low commercial viability for emerging species
- Capacity on the side of key stakeholders.

ENVIRONMENTAL VALUE LOSS

What negative impacts and costs could result from the activities envisioned for post-project exploitation, from an environmental point of view?

- Loss of high-protein fodder grasses
- Misalignment in initial rewetting calculations.

SOCIAL VALUE LOSS

What negative impacts and costs could result from the activities envisioned for post-project exploitation, from a social point of view?

- Resistance to rewetting from some actors for economic reasons, due to the association with perceived land abandonment
- Tension between past land improvement narratives of draining peatlands and the new ecological paradigm.

ECONOMIC VALUE LOSS

What negative impacts and costs could result from the activities envisioned for post-project exploitation, from an economic point of view?

- Loss of productivity for cattle and dairy sectors
- Low economic margins for biomass-based energy.

ENVIRONMENTAL VALUE CREATION

What positive impacts and benefits could result from the activities envisioned for post-project exploitation, from an environmental point of view?

- Climate mitigation through peatland rewetting
- Improved habitat conditions
- Biodiversity conservation and environmental restoration.

SOCIAL VALUE CREATION

What positive impacts and benefits could result from the activities envisioned for post-project exploitation, from a social point of view?

- Strengthened local identity and pride
- Environmental education
- Increased stakeholder participation through formats such as storytelling, excursions, and field labs.

ECONOMIC VALUE CREATION

What positive impacts and benefits could result from the activities envisioned for post-project exploitation, from an economic point of view?

- Bio-based local energy production (with one local network covering 25% of heat demand via rewetted hay)
- Funding through CAP, public programs, and private investments
- Eco-tourism.

EXPLOITATION CANVAS

Arena: Trento [The Fersina, regenerating an urban river]

BioValue's Ambitions:

Ambition 1: spatial planning safeguards, restores, allows recovery and enhances biodiversity.

Ambition 2: spatial planning significantly contributes to balanced and responsible consumption and production (avoiding external social and environmental costs).

Ambition 3: spatial planning significantly contributes to reducing socioeconomic inequalities.

About this template

The Business Model Canvas **maps** out key actors, activities and resources, the value proposition and more. Here, it has been revised to **strategise** and inform the experimentation of BioValue's research framework.

The focus is on the **post-project exploitation**, providing a template for developing a short-run (4-year) action plan and presenting it to the outside.

ARENA AMBITION

Contextualisation:

Transform how the Fersina River corridor is understood and managed, shifting from a hydraulic-infrastructure approach to a model of ecological and social regeneration, to align spatial planning with ecosystem service logic and to restore lost relationships between the river and the communities it traverses. Reframe the river as both a spatial connector and a vehicle for climate resilience, social cohesion, and health.

What is the intended post-project ambition?

Intend biodiversity not as a constraint, but as a generative force that can guide zoning, stimulate inclusive co-design, and elevate well-being. Consolidate this model through new governance practices, planning standards, and monitoring strategies embedded in municipal and provincial frameworks (revision of the General Regulatory Plan).

IMPLEMENTATION ACTIVITIES AND ROADMAP

What activities will the Arena ambition and transformative change be achieved through?

- Launch of SEA/PRG coordination work
- Development of pilot project concept and participatory validation
- Execution of €100,000 pilot project
- Finalisation of Fersina Masterplan with scenario-based zoning and ES mapping
- Launch of voluntary SEA for the Masterplan
- Voluntary environmental monitoring before and after execution.

What exploitation roadmap is envisioned to reach the intended post-project ambition?

- Creation of an interdepartmental biodiversity coordination unit
- Possible replications of BioValue methods in similar regional Rivers
- More frequent adoption of participatory procedures into municipal planning regulations
- Continuous evaluation and data feedback into PRG monitoring.

CONTRIBUTION AND RESULTS FROM BIOVALUE

Detail the role of Key Exploitable Results in the Arena:

- **ER1:** Enabled a redefinition of the Fersina River corridor as a socio-ecological infrastructure, elevated biodiversity and ES to drivers of urban transformation, and supported narrative framing for political communication and funding proposals
- **ER2:** Delivered mapping techniques, causal logic tools, ES assessment frameworks, and scenario design methods scaled into real planning processes (Masterplan, PRG, SEA), and contributed to design spatial indicators for regulatory zoning
- **ER3:** Structured multi-actor governance, aligned planning and environmental procedures across departments, and generated momentum for voluntary SEA and to integrate participatory milestones in PRG updates.

Terms of contributions during the project: BioValue

- Positioned biodiversity and ES as central pillars in Trento's urban planning narrative
- Created an enabling environment for cross-sector collaboration through facilitation and participatory planning formats
- Provided planning legitimacy and technical justification to integrate ES mapping and governance reform into the PRG revision.

In terms of post-project potential:

- BioValue's methods will be used to design and assess future scenarios along the neighbouring rivers
- The approach is transferable to other Italian cities addressing river-based urban regeneration
- The causal map tool and facilitation formats will be adapted for school programmes and civic learning.

KEY STAKEHOLDERS AND MAIN ACTORS

Which stakeholders do you expect to be most relevant for the post-project exploitation?

- Municipality of Trento (Urban Planning, Regeneration, Environmental Transition departments, Parks and Gardens Office)
- Province of Trento (PAT)
- Academic and technical partners (University of Trento)
- Local associations and NGOs (Ecomuseo Argentario, Associazione Pescatori Trentini, SAT, and other civic associations)
- Health and education (Azienda Sanitaria, Liceo Galilei, primary schools)
- Community representatives (neighbourhood councils and residents along the river)
- Private and hybrid actors (energy providers, consultants involved in masterplanning processes).

KEY INSTRUMENTS AND TOOLS

Which instruments do you expect to employ for the post-project exploitation?

- **SP&Ms:** Biodiversity-based zoning overlays (e.g. ES hotspots, urban cooling zones), spatial guidelines in the PRG and Green Plan
- **EAIs:** SEA methodology tailored for green infrastructure, use of indicators for carbon sequestration, habitat quality, flood retention
- **E&Fs:** Betterment levies and land value capture, sponsorships and crowdfunding (including to support the Canyon Park development), experimental PES (Payment for Ecosystem Services) schemes in development.

VALUE PROPOSITION

What motivates the intervention in the specific Arena context? What transformations will be achieved in your Arena? How do these relate to and build towards the post-project ambition?

The intervention is driven by the gap between the Fersina River's ecological potential and its heavy anthropization in Trento's urban fabric. The river's fragmentation highlights the need to reconnect nature, communities, and urban policy. The Arena aims to transform the river corridor into a socio-ecological infrastructure - enhancing biodiversity, public health, and social inclusion through ecosystem service-based planning.

POLICY AND SPATIAL PLANNING FRAMEWORK

Which spatial planning law and regulations impact your Arena?

How is the regulatory environment expected to affect the post-project exploitation?

The policy and regulatory framework is shaped primarily by the General Regulatory Plan (PRG). Through BioValue, key principles such as green-blue infrastructure, accessibility, and ES-based prioritisation are being introduced into Article 86 of the planning code, which governs river buffer zones. The PRG revision process is also supported by the Urban Green Plan and the Building Code, particularly in terms of climate adaptation and the implementation of nature-based solutions. The voluntary application of Strategic Environmental Assessment (SEA) to the Fersina Masterplan has demonstrated how traditional assessment tools can be reinterpreted as proactive instruments of transformation. Post-project, the Arena expects these frameworks to institutionalise BioValue methods, embedding participatory procedures, biodiversity indicators, and scenario-based planning into official spatial instruments.

KEY RESOURCES

Which resources are expected to be crucial for the post-project exploitation?

- **Institutional resources:** Political mandate and planning legitimacy provided by the Municipality of Trento and PAT, formal governance instruments such as the Protocol of Objectives and planning mandates
- **Human resources:** Cross-sectoral technical staff (urban planners, engineers, ecologists), community engagement facilitators and school programme coordinators
- **Knowledge and data:** Ecosystem service maps and hydrological simulations, co-created knowledge from participatory mapping and scenario building
- **Financial resources:** Municipal investment lines (pilot project funding secured), EU programme access (LIFE, Interreg, Horizon), private sector partnerships for specific sites (e.g. Canyon Park).

Which ones are not currently present and will have to be sourced or developed?

Long-term facilitation and mediation capabilities, mechanisms for inter-institutional alignment with PAT, legal design for PES and hybrid E&P tools.

BARRIERS AND CHALLENGES

Which are the main barriers and challenges foreseen for post-project exploitation?

- Fragmented governance between municipal and provincial authorities
- Resistance to reducing infrastructure, especially car based, dominance in river spaces
- Lack of integration with valuation of ecosystem services
- Risk of political shifts deprioritising long-term biodiversity goals
- Difficulties in aligning sectoral logics (e.g. engineering, health, environment)
- Limited staff time and budget for process facilitation and co-creation.

ENVIRONMENTAL VALUE LOSS

What negative impacts and costs could result from the activities envisioned for post-project exploitation, from an environmental point of view?

- Risk of ecologically unsound river redevelopment
- Risk of pressure on river habitat due to tourism over-development
- Possible symbolic use of ES terms
- Risk of reduced habitat quality.

ENVIRONMENTAL VALUE CREATION

What positive impacts and benefits could result from the activities envisioned for post-project exploitation, from an environmental point of view?

- Riparian habitat restoration
- Improved flood resilience and green infrastructure connectivity
- Nature-based urban cooling and increased biodiversity near urban areas.

SOCIAL VALUE LOSS

What negative impacts and costs could result from the activities envisioned for post-project exploitation, from a social point of view?

- Loss of trust if participatory promises are not fulfilled
- Potential reinforcement of spatial inequalities
- Risk of gentrification for the Clarina neighbourhood.

SOCIAL VALUE CREATION

What positive impacts and benefits could result from the activities envisioned for post-project exploitation, from a social point of view?

- Stronger civic identity
- Health benefits
- Educational opportunities via school involvement
- Empowered neighbourhoods through engagement and co-design.

ECONOMIC VALUE LOSS

What negative impacts and costs could result from the activities envisioned for post-project exploitation, from an economic point of view?

- Possible inefficiencies in land use
- Risk of high costs due to vegetation maintenance in urban sector of the river

ECONOMIC VALUE CREATION

What positive impacts and benefits could result from the activities envisioned for post-project exploitation, from an economic point of view?

- Improved planning efficiency
- "Green" job creation
- Climate adaptation savings
- Attraction of public-private investment and improved access to EU funding streams
- Financial self-management of the Canyon park through revenue of Orrido di Ponte Alto ecomuseum and other activities.

EXPLOITATION CANVAS

Arena: Mafra [Municipal Spatial Planning]

BioValue's Ambitions:

Ambition 1: spatial planning safeguards, restores, allows recovery and enhances biodiversity.

Ambition 2: spatial planning significantly contributes to balanced and responsible consumption and production (avoiding external social and environmental costs).

Ambition 3: spatial planning significantly contributes to reducing socioeconomic inequalities.

About this template

The Business Model Canvas **maps** out key actors, activities and resources, the value proposition and more. Here, it has been revised to **strategise** and inform the experimentation of BioValue's research framework.

The focus is on the **post-project exploitation**, providing a template for developing a short-run (4-year) action plan and presenting it to the outside.

ARENA AMBITION

Contextualisation:

Promote a planning system in Mafra that proactively safeguards biodiversity and ecological values beyond existing legal frameworks, addressing the high tourism pressure through planning strategies that preserve green and blue infrastructure, ecological connectivity, and ecosystem services.

What is the intended post-project ambition?

Recognise biodiversity as a strategic municipal asset and embed it across sectors including agriculture, tourism, water management, education, and housing, aligning local spatial planning with BioValue's ambitions of biodiversity restoration (Ambition 1), responsible land use (Ambition 2) and reducing socioeconomic inequalities (Ambition 3), by implementing a municipal fund for environmental and urban sustainability and payment for ecosystems services in rural areas.

KEY STAKEHOLDERS AND MAIN ACTORS

Which stakeholders do you expect to be most relevant for the post-project exploitation?

- Municipality of Mafra
- Local agrifood actors, water management authorities, and landowners
- Tourism operators and cultural institutions
- Civil society (local NGOs, educators, citizens' associations)
- National and regional authorities
- School community.

POLICY AND SPATIAL PLANNING FRAMEWORK

Which spatial planning law and regulations impact your Arena?

How is the regulatory environment expected to affect the post-project exploitation?

The arena operates under Portugal's national spatial planning law and municipal regulations (Revised PDM of Mafra). Biodiversity is acknowledged, but does not yet represent a driver of land-use decisions; SEA and EIA are implemented, but do not prioritise biodiversity enhancement; current planning complies with the minimum legal standards. Mafra's experience can contribute to future national-level guidelines on biodiversity in spatial planning, including by possibly integrating within future regulation an ecosystems services - related approach to the planning system, currently present only as an orientation.

IMPLEMENTATION ACTIVITIES AND ROADMAP

What activities will the Arena ambition and transformative change be achieved through?

- Embed biodiversity and ecosystem services in PDM revision and implementation
- Develop and disseminate biodiversity-sensitive planning guidelines at municipal level
- Continue training and awareness activities for municipal departments and sectoral stakeholders
- Expand green and blue infrastructure initiatives (nature-based solutions, connectivity planning)
- Strengthen participatory planning tools tested in BioValue.

What exploitation roadmap is envisioned to reach the intended post-project ambition?

- Institutionalise co-creation processes and evidence-informed planning
- Mobilise internal and external funding for biodiversity actions
- Create a monitoring framework for biodiversity outcomes
- Disseminate best practices to other Portuguese municipalities.

KEY INSTRUMENTS AND TOOLS

Which instruments do you expect to employ for the post-project exploitation?

- **SP&MIs:** Green and blue infrastructure strategy, ecosystem services mapping and integration into the revised PDM, spatial connectivity planning and land-use designations supporting biodiversity, Municipal Building and Urbanization Regulations of the Municipality of Mafra
- **EAs:** Stakeholder engagement formats tested in BioValue workshops, scenario planning for biodiversity under tourism and land-use pressures, ecosystem-based SEA and EIA enhancement tools, causal map tool of cause-effect relations and biodiversity mitigation hierarchy connected to spatial planning
- **E&Es:** Municipal environmental sustainability funds, financial mechanisms for land conservation and nature-based solutions, frameworks to valorise biodiversity in decision-making (e.g. land value adjustment, PES), environmental fund and Ecosystems Services Fund, Municipality of Mafra Fee Regulations and respective fee schedule.

KEY RESOURCES

Which resources are expected to be crucial for the post-project exploitation?

- **Human and organisational capacity:** internal staff with planning and environmental expertise, local NGOs and researchers mobilised through BioValue, education and awareness-raising formats from workshops
 - **Financial and economic resources:** support from national sustainability funds (e.g. Fundo Municipal de Sustentabilidade Ambiental e Urbanística), EU-level support (LIFE, Horizon Europe, Interreg), municipal budget allocated to green and blue infrastructure
 - **Database Resources:** open data on biodiversity-related indicators in Mafra's spatial planning monitoring system (<https://spmi-canvas.mafra.gov.pt/data-arena/csm>)
- Which ones are not currently present and will have to be sourced or developed?**
Integration of ecosystem service mapping in spatial databases, capacity-building for sectoral actors in biodiversity-sensitive planning, cross-sectoral working groups within the municipality.

CONTRIBUTION AND RESULTS FROM BIOVALUE

Detail the role of Key Exploitable Results in the Arena

- **E&E1:** Helped identify gaps in the current spatial planning cycle and proposed how biodiversity can be better mainstreamed in the revised PDM, supporting the conceptual integration of ecosystem services and multifunctional land-use design
- **E&E2:** Provided methods and instruments (e.g. ecosystem services mapping, participatory formats), enabled alignment between municipal planning and biodiversity targets beyond legal minimums and contributed to the planning vision for green/blue infrastructure in connection with water management, tourism and agrifood sectors
- **E&E3:** Informed on how to institutionalise co-creation and stakeholder engagement, helped define potential funding strategies and monitoring mechanisms, and provided best practices for ecosystem-oriented planning.

In terms of contributions during the project, BioValue:

- Enabled a shared vocabulary and structure to link scientific evidence with local planning practices
- Created a foundation for cross-departmental collaboration within the Municipality of Mafra
- Developed training and facilitation approaches tailored to the policy and planning context.

In terms of post-project potential:

- Mafra can serve as a demonstration site for ecosystem-based planning within national and EU dialogues - Mafra as a front-runner to mainstream and scale-up BioValue activities
- Tools and methods developed (e.g. participatory workshops, causal map tool, ES framework) can be adapted by other municipalities
- The arena's cross-sectoral ambition offers a replicable governance model to integrate biodiversity across departments and policies.

VALUE PROPOSITION

What motivates the intervention in the specific Arena context? What transformations will be achieved in your Arena? How do these relate to and build towards the post-project ambition?

BioValue aims to facilitate a biodiversity-driven transformation of Mafra's spatial planning practices, positioning the municipality as a reference for integrating natural value into land-use decisions, going beyond minimum compliance and showcasing how biodiversity enhances resilience, quality of life, and sustainable tourism. This involves building strategic partnerships, mobilising funding, and anchoring biodiversity within municipal policies and spatial planning instruments.

Mafra aims to integrate biodiversity through spatial planning in activities such as tourism, agriculture activities, housing, and urbanisation, engaging policymakers and influencing political agendas towards increasing biodiversity and implementing specific actions (including ecological restoration and renaturalisation of urban areas).

BARRIERS AND CHALLENGES

Which are the main barriers and challenges foreseen for post-project exploitation?

- Limited internal capacity to develop and monitor biodiversity metrics
- Fragmentation between policy sectors and planning competencies
- Difficulty in shifting from a reactive to a proactive planning culture
- Dependence on external funding and expertise to sustain innovation
- Risk of low institutional uptake of participatory and co-creation processes tested within BioValue
- Tension between conservation aims and dominant economic narratives (tourism, housing, political agenda).

ENVIRONMENTAL VALUE LOSS

What negative impacts and costs could result from the activities envisioned for post-project exploitation, from an environmental point of view?

- Risk of superficial or symbolic integration of biodiversity in planning (e.g. "greenwashing" strategies)
- Misalignment between biodiversity objectives and tourism or urban expansion agendas
- Potential overreliance on ecosystem service proxies without strong ecological baselines
- Possible neglect of soil and microhabitat dynamics if spatial planning focuses on large-scale features only.

ENVIRONMENTAL VALUE CREATION

What positive impacts and benefits could result from the activities envisioned for post-project exploitation, from an environmental point of view?

- Support for biodiversity conservation and ecological connectivity across urban, rural, and coastal areas
- Enhanced use of green and blue infrastructure to mitigate fragmentation and climate risks
- Integration of ecosystem services into land-use decisions at municipal level
- Strategic protection of natural heritage as a foundation for sustainable tourism and quality of life
- Demonstration of how spatial planning can become a tool for ecological regeneration.

SOCIAL VALUE LOSS

What negative impacts and costs could result from the activities envisioned for post-project exploitation, from a social point of view?

- Resistance from stakeholders unaccustomed to biodiversity-sensitive planning
- Potential exclusion of certain groups from participatory processes
- Perception that ecological priorities may limit traditional land-use practices or development opportunities, for tourism and housing.

SOCIAL VALUE CREATION

What positive impacts and benefits could result from the activities envisioned for post-project exploitation, from a social point of view?

- Strengthened citizen knowledge and capacity through engagement and participatory processes focused on the importance of biodiversity (links with education)
- Capacity-building among municipal staff, educators and community stakeholders
- Increased environmental literacy and sense of stewardship across sectors
- Reinforcement of Mafra's identity as a biodiversity-conscious, naturally and culturally rich territory.

ECONOMIC VALUE LOSS

What negative impacts and costs could result from the activities envisioned for post-project exploitation, from an economic point of view?

- Short-term costs linked to ecosystem restoration, mapping, and monitoring
- Investment needs for updating planning tools, staff training, and infrastructure
- Risk of friction with economic actors if spatial planning introduces land-use restrictions.

ECONOMIC VALUE CREATION

What positive impacts and benefits could result from the activities envisioned for post-project exploitation, from an economic point of view?

- Diversification of local economy through eco-tourism and sustainable land-use practices
- Improved access to EU and national biodiversity-related funding streams
- Long-term savings via nature-based solutions for water, climate adaptation, and health
- Potential to attract innovation in biodiversity planning and monitoring.

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